

ERA4 HEALTH PROJECT

ANNOTATED TEMPLATE MODEL FOR AN EU CLINICAL SITE AGREEMENT (“EU CSA”)

NOTA BENE: This is a living document. It might be updated in the second stage of the project and thus replaced with a new version. For reasons of confidentiality and protection of personal data, and since the document will be widely spread, the names of the members of the Legal task force will not be shared together with the document.

INSTRUCTIONS: The instructions for filling out this contract model are marked in red and blue
Please select the relevant option and delete the ones that do not apply (see Options in red) and fill out the missing information (see Fields to fill in blue)

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AGREEMENT FOR THE CONDUCT OF THE CLINICAL TRIAL

Hereinafter referred to as “Clinical site agreement or CSA”

[Insert title of Clinical trial and title of EU project if the clinical trial is funded under an EU program]

Clinical trial ID: *[Insert Registration number and date (e.g. EUDRACT number)]*

[If applicable, insert name and function(s) of Coordinating Investigator]

Coordinating Investigator: *[Insert name and function(s)]*

Principal Investigator : *[Insert name, function(s) and country]*

THIS AGREEMENT IS MADE BY AND BETWEEN (hereinafter referred to as the “**Agreement**”):

[Insert name of Sponsor], whose registered office *[Insert registration number]* is at *[Insert address]*, represented by *[Insert name(s) and function(s)]*

Hereinafter referred to as “Sponsor”

And

[Insert name of Clinical site Institution], whose registered office *[Insert registration number]* is at *[Insert address]*, represented by *[Insert name(s) and function(s)]*

Hereinafter referred to as “Clinical Site ”

Hereinafter individually or collectively referred to as the “Party” or the “Parties”.

WHEREAS

The Sponsor of the Clinical trial wishes to enter into an agreement with Clinical Site to conduct the Clinical trial according to this Agreement and its Appendices.

SELECT THE RELEVANT OPTION (depending on the source of funding)

OPTION 1 [within EU Funding program framework][if not applicable, please delete and/or replace]

The Clinical trial “[*Include full title*]” with protocol code “[*Include protocol code if applicable*]” and EUCT number [*Include EUCT number*] (the “Trial”) is part of the project “[*Insert full title and acronym*]” funded through the EU Funding program [*Insert name of the funding program, e.g. Horizon Europe, other*] under the Grant agreement No. “[*Include GA Number*]”.

The Sponsor is considered a [*Select status under the GA: either Beneficiary or Third Party*] (see Definitions below) under the Grant Agreement.

Select the right option:

OPTION 2 [other source of funding]

The Clinical trial “[*Include full title*]” with protocol code “[*Include protocol code if applicable*]” and EUCT number [*Include EUCT number*] (the “Trial”) is part of the project “[*Insert full title and acronym*]”

The Trial is funded by [*Insert name of the funding program or funding source if no program*]

The Sponsor has assigned the responsibility for the coordination of the investigators to [*Insert name and affiliation*] (the « Coordinating investigator)

Select the right option:

OPTION 1: Insert the following sentence if Clinical trial funded by an EU Funding program framework][if not applicable, please delete and/or replace this sentence]The Coordinating investigator is [*Select role and affiliation: employee, consultant, etc*] of [*Insert name of Coordinating Investigator Institution*] which acts as a [*Select status of the Institution under the GA: either beneficiary or THIRD PARTY*] to the Grant Agreement.

The Clinical site has appointed as principal investigator responsible for the conduct of the Clinical trial at the site [*Insert Name of PI, MD*] (hereinafter the “PI”).

OPTION 2: Insert the following sentence if Clinical trial funded by an EU Funding program framework][if not applicable, please delete and/or replace this sentence]

The Clinical site is a [*Select status under the EU GA: either Beneficiary or THIRD PARTY (see Definitions below)*] to the Grant Agreement.

THEREFORE, IT IS HEREBY AGREED AS FOLLOWS:

The Parties hereto intend to enter into this agreement (hereinafter the “Agreement”) in order to specify their mutual rights and obligations with respect to the Trial.

1. PURPOSE OF THE AGREEMENT

The purpose of this Agreement is:

1. to set out the rights, responsibilities, and obligations of the Parties regarding the conduct of the Trial at the Clinical Site
2. to define the responsibilities and obligations of the Parties in relation to the personal data processing activities involved in the conduct of the Trial

2. DEFINITIONS

[Background information: The clinical trials definitions below are based mainly on the definitions provided under the Clinical Trial Regulation EU No 536/2014 (“the CTR”). In the absence of a definition within the CTR, the ICH E6(R3) Guideline Definitions have been utilized as a model.]

[a List of Definitions is provided below. If not applicable, please delete and/or replace]

“Applicable Regulatory Requirement(s)” means any applicable law(s) and regulation(s) addressing the conduct of clinical trials of investigational products (ICH E6(R3) Guideline, Glossary, p. 70);

“Case Report Form” or **“CRF”** means the case report forms in the form provided or approved by the Sponsor to be used by the Principal Investigator and the Clinical Site Team Members to record relevant data related to the Clinical Trial;

“Clinical Site” means the location(s) where trial-related activities are conducted and/or coordinated under the investigator’s/institution’s oversight. (ICH E6(R3) Guideline, Glossary, p. 75);

“Clinical site agreement” (“The CSA”) means agreement contract between the Sponsor and the clinical site.

“Clinical trial Regulation EU No 536/2014” (“the CTR”) means REGULATION (EU) No 536/2014 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 16 April 2014 on clinical trials on medicinal products for human use, and repealing Directive 2001/20/EC (OJ L 158 27.5.2014, p. 1);

“Clinical trial” means a clinical study which fulfils any of the following conditions:

(a) the assignment of the subject to a particular therapeutic strategy is decided in advance and does not fall within normal clinical practice of the Member State concerned.

(b) the decision to prescribe the investigational medicinal products is taken together with the decision to include the subject in the clinical study; or

(c) diagnostic or monitoring procedures in addition to normal clinical practice are applied to the subjects. (Clinical Trial Regulation EU No 536/2014, Article 2 Definitions, OJ L 158 27.5.2014, p. 1)

“Clinical Trial Authorisation” means an authorisation granted in accordance with the CTR or other applicable national law in the jurisdiction of the Trial Site;

“Clinical Trials Legislation” means all legislation and regulations relating to the conduct of clinical trials in [*INSERT COUNTRY(s) WHERE TRIAL WILL BE CARRIED OUT*], as applicable to the Clinical Trial, including the Regulation (EU) 536/2014 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 April 2014 on clinical trials on medicinal products for human use and all other statutory instruments, guidelines (whether statutory or non-statutory) or codes of practice or guidance issued by a Regulatory Authority relating to clinical trials and any amendments thereto;

“Data Controller” or? **“Controller”** means the natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, **alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data;**

“Data Processor” shall have the meaning given to the term “processor” in Article 4 of the GDPR;

“Data Protection Laws and regulations” means all law, legislation and regulations relating to the protection of Personal Data applicable to a Party including (without limitation) the local data protection laws and regulations, the GDPR and all other statutory instruments;

“Data Subject” shall have the meaning given to that term in Article 4 of the GDPR;

“Ethics Committee” means a committee established or recognized in accordance with Clinical Trials Legislation or other applicable national law in the jurisdiction of the Trial Site;

“Funder” means [*Indicate the Name of the funder/program or the source of funding*];

“Funding Agreement” means the Agreement as attached at Schedule x;

“GDPR” means the General Data Protection Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2016/679);

“Good Clinical Practice” or **“GCP”** includes the ICH Harmonised Tripartite Guideline for Good Clinical Practice (CPMP/ICH/135/95) together with such other good clinical practice requirements as are specified in the Clinical Trials Legislation and European Commission Directive 2005/28/EC of 8 April 2005 laying down principles and detailed guidelines for good clinical practice as regards investigational medicinal products for human use, as well as the requirements for authorisation of the manufacturing or importation of such products and in guidance published by the European Commission pursuant to the foregoing;]

“Investigational Medicinal Product” means the trial drug or control material as defined in the Protocol;

“**Loss**” includes any claim, suit, proceeding, judgement, loss, liability, cost, expense, fee, penalty or fine;

“**Medical Records**” means primary medical records kept by the Clinical Organisation in relation to the treatment of a Participant;

“**Participant**” means an individual, whether a patient or not, who participates in the Trial according to criteria detailed in the Protocol;

“**Personal Data**” means personal data as defined in Data Protection Law;

“**Personal Data Discloser**” means the Trial Site when it discloses Shared Data to the Sponsor;

“**Personal Data Recipient**” means the Sponsor when it receives Shared Data from the Personal Data Discloser;

“**Processing**” means any operation or set of operations which is performed on Personal Data or on sets of Personal Data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction (and “**Process**” and “**Processed**” should be construed accordingly);

“**Pseudonymisation**” shall have the meaning given to that term in Article 4 of the GDPR and “**pseudonymise**”, “**pseudonymised**” and “**pseudonymises**” should be construed accordingly);

“Regulatory Authority” includes, but is not limited to, the regulatory authority in country where trial site is located, the European Medicines Agency and such other regulatory authorities as may have jurisdiction over the Clinical Site;

“Site File” means the file maintained by the Principal Investigator containing the documentation specified in section 8 of ICH Good Clinical Practice (edition CPMP/ICH/135/95);

“SOP” means the Standard Operating Procedures applicable to the conduct of the Clinical Trial;

“Term” means the period beginning on the Commencement Date and ending on the date on which this Agreement expires or is terminated pursuant to Clause 19 (*term & termination*);

“Clinical Site Team Members” means the persons who undertake the conduct of the Trial at the Clinical Site under the supervision of the Principal Investigator;

“Comparator” means an investigational or authorized medicinal product (i.e., active control), placebo or standard of care used as a reference in a Trial. (ICH E6(R3) Guideline, Glossary, p. 70);

“Investigator” means an individual responsible for the conduct of a trial at a Clinical Site (Clinical trial Regulation EU No 536/2014, Article 2 Definitions, OJ L 158 27.5.2014, p. 1);

“Principal investigator” (“The PI”) means an investigator who is the responsible leader of a team of investigators who conduct a Trial at a Clinical Site (Clinical trial Regulation EU No 536/2014, Article 2 Definitions, OJ L 158 27.5.2014, p. 1);

“Coordinating Investigator” means an investigator assigned the responsibility for the coordination of investigators at different investigator sites participating in a multicenter trial. (ICH E6(R3) Guideline, Glossary, p. 70);

“Coordinating center” means a national Clinical Site assigned the responsibility for the coordination of National Clinical sites participating in a multinational trial. [after the definition of coordinating investigator under (ICH E6(R3) Guideline, Glossary, p. 77);

“Early termination of a clinical trial” means the premature end of a Clinical trial due to any reason before the conditions specified in the protocol are complied with (Clinical trial Regulation EU No 536/2014, Article 2 Definitions, OJ L 158 27.5.2014, p. 1);

“EU Grants” means grants awarded by EU institutions, bodies, offices or agencies (including EU executive agencies, EU regulatory agencies, EDA, joint undertakings, etc.) (EU Grants: AGA — Annotated Grant Agreement: V2.0– 01.04.2025);

“Inspection” means the act by a competent authority of conducting an official review of documents, facilities, records, quality assurance arrangements, and any other resources that are deemed by the

competent authority to be related to the clinical trial and that may be located at the Clinical Site, at the sponsor's and/or contract research organisation's facilities, or at other establishments which the competent authority sees fit to inspect (Clinical trial Regulation EU No 536/2014, Article 2 Definitions, OJ L 158 27.5.2014, p. 1);

“Human biological material” means any human biological product such as tissues and cells derived from the human body and their derivatives, organs, blood, its components and derivatives

Protocol means a document that describes the objectives, design, methodology, statistical considerations and organization of a Trial. The term ‘protocol’ encompasses successive versions of the protocol and protocol modifications (Clinical Trial Regulation EU No 536/2014, Article 2 Definitions, OJ L 158 27.5.2014, p. 1);

“Sponsor” means an individual, company, institution or organization which takes responsibility for the initiation, for the management and for setting up the financing of the Trial (Clinical trial Regulation EU No 536/2014, Article 2 Definitions, OJ L 158 27.5.2014, p. 1);

“Co-Sponsor” means where a Trial has more than one sponsor and each co-sponsor assume the liabilities and responsibilities as defined under the **CTR** unless otherwise specified in a written agreement between the co-sponsors;

“Third Party under EU Grants” means legal entities which participate in the action but are not considered Beneficiaries to the EU Grant. They can be either affiliated entities, or in-kind contributors or subcontractors. (EU Grants: AGA — Annotated Grant Agreement: V2.0– 01.04.2025);

“Beneficiaries (BEN) under EU Grants”— The signatories of the EU Grant agreement (either directly or through an accession form). (EU Grants: AGA — Annotated Grant Agreement: V2.0– 01.04.2025);

“Affiliated entities (AE) under EU Grants” means Entities affiliated to a beneficiary within the meaning of Article 190 of EU Financial Regulation 2024/250912 which participate in the action with similar rights and obligations as the beneficiaries (obligation to implement action tasks and right to charge costs and claim contributions). (EU Grants: AGA — Annotated Grant Agreement: V2.0– 01.04.2025);

“Associated partners (AP) under EU Grant” means Entities which participate in the action, but without the right to charge costs or claim contributions. (EU Grants: AGA — Annotated Grant Agreement: V2.0– 01.04.2025);

“Subcontracting under EU Grants” means Contracts for goods, works or services that are part of the action tasks (see Annex 1) (EU Grants: AGA — Annotated Grant Agreement: V2.0– 01.04.2025);

“In-kind contributions under the EU Grants” means subcontractors within the meaning of Article 2(38) of EU Financial Regulation 2024/2509, i.e. non-financial resources made available free of charge by third parties. (EU Grants: AGA — Annotated Grant Agreement: V2.0– 01.04.2025);

3. QUALIFICATION OF THE CLINICAL TRIAL

- According to the current Protocol, the Trial falls under the category of “Clinical trials on medicinal products for human use” as defined under the Clinical trial Regulation EU No 536/2014
- Should the qualification of the Trial be modified following the regulatory submissions or due to changes in the protocol or any other reason, the Sponsor should notify immediately the Clinical Site and the PI, and the present Agreement should be modified accordingly.

4. REQUIREMENTS FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE AGREEMENT

4.1. Legal and regulatory requirements

The Parties shall act:

4.1.1. In accordance with the Protocol as approved by the Sponsor and the relevant authorities (see Appendix x), with their respective roles and responsibilities as described in the present Agreement and the Tasks list referred to in the Section Duties of this Agreement.

4.1.2. Initiate the Trial within the Clinical Site only after all necessary legal, regulatory or other required approvals or opinions have been granted including, without limitation, those of the competent authority, the competent ethics committee, the data supervisory authority as applicable, and strictly in accordance with the terms of any of such approval.

4.1.3. In accordance with the requirements laid down by laws and regulations applicable in the country where the Trial is conducted and the Clinical Site is located.

4.1.4. According to the European Union Clinical Trials Regulation (regulation (EU) No 536/2014) relating to the conduct of clinical trials on investigational medicinal products (“the CTR”), the Declaration of Helsinki (latest updated version), the principles of Good Clinical Practice as laid down by the ICH HARMONISED GUIDELINE FOR GOOD CLINICAL PRACTICE E6(R3) (ICH E6 R3) (Final version, Adopted on 06 January 2025) (hereinafter referred to as “GCP”) and the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and

of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (“the GDPR”) and any related law and regulations applicable in the participating countries, including but not limited to the local legal and regulatory insurance related requirements for compensation for any damage suffered by the Trial participants from participation in the Trial.

4.2. Legal and regulatory requirements in the event of Co-sponsorship

[This section applies when the Sponsor has entered into a Co-Sponsorship agreement; if not applicable, please delete this section]

- 4.2.1. The Co-Sponsors of the Clinical trial are [*Insert name of Co-Sponsors and legal address*]
- 4.2.2. The Co-Sponsors responsibilities in relation to the Trial are described in the Appendix xxx [*Attach Description of the Co-sponsors responsibilities as per the Co-Sponsorship agreement*]
- 4.2.3. The Sponsor represents that none of the responsibilities assigned to the other Co-Sponsor(s) have an impact on the role and responsibilities of the Clinical Site requiring the Co-Sponsors to be a Party to the present Agreement; in the event of changes in the responsibilities of the Co-sponsors, the Sponsor should notify the Clinical Site as soon as it becomes aware and amend the present Agreement accordingly;
- 4.2.4. If need be, the Co-Sponsor should become a Party to the present Agreement

4.2.5. Notwithstanding the above, as per Article 72 of the CTR, the Sponsors shall be jointly responsible for establishing:

a) a Sponsor responsible for compliance with the obligations of a sponsor in the authorization procedures set out in Chapters II and III of the CTR.

b) a Sponsor responsible for being a contact point for receiving all questions from subjects, investigators or any Member State concerned regarding the clinical trial and providing answers to them.

c) a Sponsor responsible for implementing the measures taken in accordance with Article 77 of the CTR

4.2.6. As provided under the CTR, where the Agreement does not specify to which Sponsor a given responsibility is attributed, that responsibility shall lie with all Sponsors.

4.3. Requirements related to the “investigational medicinal product(s)” and any other research investigations

[The requirements might differ from country to country. Model requirements clauses are provided below (in italics) If not applicable, please delete and/or adapt based on the national legal requirements if different]

- The “**xxxx**” (hereinafter the “Clinical trial medicinal product(s)”) is/are being tested in the Clinical trial.
- The “**xxxx**” is/are being used as “reference medicinal product(s)” in the Clinical trial.

- *According to the Protocol, the following the additional diagnostic or monitoring procedures in addition to normal clinical practice are applied to the subjects: **[Indicate if the protocol includes other procedures added by research to normal clinical practice such as taking blood sample(s), etc.]***
- *The following activities/procedures fall within normal clinical practice **[list the activities that fall within the 'normal clinical practice']**.*
- *The Clinical trial medicinal product(s) will be distributed by "xxxx" and the costs associated with will be ...as described in Budget agreement (see Appendix xxx) **[Indicate if multiple distribution points]**The Clinical trial medicinal product(s) will be provided by the Sponsor and delivered to the Clinical Site or the local pharmacy appointed by the Clinical Site at no costs to the Clinical Site*
- *Unused, partly unused or expired, the Investigational medicinal(s) product must be destroyed according to local procedures at the Clinical Site upon approval by the Sponsor.*
- *Should additional medicinal product(s) be used either as investigational products or reference medicinal products in the conduct of the Clinical trial, the Parties shall amend the Agreement accordingly prior to such use.*

4.4. Requirements related to Clinical trial insurance and indemnification [*Model insurance clauses are provided below (in italics). If not applicable, please delete and/or replace the following examples*]

Model 1 : Most common situations across the EU. When the Sponsor doesn't fall under the status of "self-insured" organization [if not applicable in your country, please delete and/or adapt based on the national legal requirements if different]

- *The Sponsor agrees to take out adequate Clinical Trial insurance as required by applicable legal and regulatory requirements to provide compensation to participants in the Clinical trial suffering injury or death or loss caused by the administration of the product as specified in the Protocol or any clinical intervention or procedure carried out in accordance with the Protocol and all legal requirements laid down by regulations where the Clinical trial is conducted.*
- *For the avoidance of any doubt, the Clinical site is not obliged to take out any Clinical Trial insurance unless otherwise provided by the national laws and regulations.*
- *If required by the applicable regulatory requirement(s), the sponsor should provide insurance or should indemnify (legal and financial coverage) the investigator/the institution against claims arising from the Clinical trial except for claims that arise from malpractice and/or negligence*
- *The Clinical Site and the PI shall notify the Sponsor promptly upon becoming aware of a claim from a research participant for which indemnification may be sought hereunder and cooperate with Sponsor in the investigation and defense of any such claim.*

Model 2: Model for self-insured Institutions provided by Denmark [if applicable to your institution, please adapt; if not applicable in your country, please delete and/or adapt based on the national legal requirements if different]

- *Institution as a Danish public body is self-insured according to Danish law. Institution's assets are sufficient to cover any contemplated self-insured liability assumed by Institution under this Agreement. All Study subjects are covered by Danish mandatory law "Lov om klage- og*

erstatningsadgang inden for sundhedsvæsenet, kapitel 4 (lov nr. 547 af 24. juni 2005)” as amended from time to time. Institution shall not be liable for any indirect losses, consequential damages, operational losses, loss of profit or other consequential financial losses.

- *Sponsor agrees to abide by the guidelines in relation to compensation for injuries suffered by Study subject included in the Study in accordance with applicable legislation and provisions of Denmark (Bekendtgørelse af lov om produktansvar (lov nr. 61 af 20 marts 2007) and Lov om klage- og erstatningsadgang indenfor sundhedsvæsenet (lov nr. 547 af 24. juni 2005) as amended from time to time.*
- *Sponsor carries general liability and product liability. Sponsor shall secure and maintain in full force and effect through-out the performance of the Study (and following termination of the Study to cover any claims arising from the Study) insurance coverage for i) product and study design liability and ii) general liability, each such insurance coverage in amounts appropriate to cover the Sponsor’s obligations and liabilities under this Agreement and in compliance with the applicable legal and regulatory requirements.*
- *Upon request, Sponsor shall provide Institution with certificates of insurance evidencing the required insurance coverage.*

5. DUTIES OF THE PARTIES

Each Party has a duty to inform the other Party as soon as possible of any difficulties encountered in carrying out the Tasks assigned to it, and which may compromise the objectives of the Clinical trial.

5.1. Duties of the Sponsor

[Specific examples of tasks are provided below (in italics). If not applicable, please delete and/or replace the following examples]

The SPONSOR shall be responsible for:

- *the management and coordination of the Clinical trial in compliance with the applicable EU and national laws and regulations and any applicable regulatory requirements in the countries.*
- ***[If not applicable, please delete and/or replace with a reference to the appropriate funding source]*** *ensure compliance with rules of the Grant Agreement [Insert registration number] and the Consortium Agreement as applicable.*
- *ensuring that all necessary authorisations, regulatory approvals, and permissions have been obtained prior to the inclusion of the research participants into the Clinical trial. [The site may be responsible for getting informed consent. Also, a coordinating centre/investigator may be responsible for obtaining some approvals, etc. If this is the case, please clarify this by specifying who is responsible]*
- ensure training and training material to the PI and the Clinical site personnel on the conduct of the Clinical trial and content of the Protocol
- *ensuring risk-appropriate monitoring of the Clinical trial, central data management and analysis of the Clinical trial data.*

- *preparing regular reports, including safety reports, for information to the Clinical site and the Ethics Committees and Competent Authorities, according to applicable regulatory requirements in the participating country.*
 - *registering the Clinical trial in CTIS and keep the database always updated during the Clinical trial period.*
 - *ensuring an adequate Clinical trial Insurance as required by applicable law and regulatory requirements.*
 - *notifying the Clinical site about the Clinical trial end or early discontinuation*
 - *undertaking any reasonable effort to publish the results of the Clinical trial in peer-reviewed journals.*
 - *providing the Clinical site with a summary of Clinical trial results*
 - *providing the Clinical Site with an approved informed consent form and patient information sheet.*
- *It is the sole responsibility of Sponsor that information that must be provided to Clinical trial subjects as required by articles 13-14 in the GDPR are included in the informed consent forms and that the informed consent form meets the requirements in the GDPR.*

The Sponsor must strictly comply with the obligations set forth at the applicable law.

5.2. Duties of the Clinical site

[Specific examples of tasks are provided below (in italics). They are extracted from the CTR; some of them are extracted from the model agreements shared by Oslo University Hospital for the purpose of establishing this template. If not applicable, please delete and/or replace the following examples]

The Clinical site shall (**For a detailed description of the tasks, see Appendix xxx, Task delegation list**) :

- *undertake to appoint a PI for the purposes of Clinical trial who meets all requirements set forth by applicable legislation. The PI must hold the appropriate professional qualifications to practice as a healthcare professional and possess demonstrated experience in the relevant field.*
- *ensure that the PI fulfils all the tasks described in the Protocol, GCP and this Agreement*
- *be responsible for the local data management and timely completion of CRFs according to the protocol*
- *promptly notify the Sponsor of any Serious adverse events (SAE) occurring during the Clinical trial and be responsible for promptly forwarding Sponsor SAE/SAR lists and other safety reports to the responsible Ethics Committee in compliance with local requirements;*
- *ensure Agreement with local pharmacy regarding handling of Clinical trial drug if not handled by the Clinical Site;*
- *ensure that all drug handling must be in accordance with the CTR [**Specify any other regulations that are applicable e.g. Advanced Therapy Medicinal products regulation**] , Good Clinical Practice and sponsor's standard operating procedures for drug handling*
- *Institution/Principal Investigator agrees to report to Sponsor immediately but not later than twenty-four (24) hours after learning of any serious Adverse Events and other important medical events, as identified in the Protocol, affecting any Study subject in the Study. Institution/Principal Investigator further agrees to follow up such report with detailed, written reports in compliance with all applicable legal and regulatory requirements. Institution/Principal Investigator shall record and evaluate all adverse events experienced by the Study subjects in accordance with the Protocol*

- *ensure the capability, temporal availability and professional education of the Clinical trial personnel at the Clinical site to execute the tasks*
- *ensure that all investigators and personnel who participate in the conduct of the Trial are informed of and comply with the terms of this Agreement.*
- *in case of delegation of tasks by the Sponsor to a third party (e.g. Clinical trial-related monitoring tasks, or regulatory audits and inspections) the Clinical Site shall , in accordance with applicable regulatory requirements and the provisions of the present Agreement, permit access to source records and any other required documents for the performance of the tasks; For the avoidance of any doubt, the tasks delegated by the Sponsor to third parties shall be described in detail in Appendix 1.*
- *all Clinical trial information shall be recorded, processed, handled, and stored by Clinical Site, as applicable, in such a way that it can be accurately reported, interpreted and verified while the confidentiality of records and the personal data of the subjects remain protected in accordance with the applicable law on personal data protection.*
- *unless other Union law requires archiving for a longer period, the Clinical Site shall archive the content of the Clinical trial master file for at least 25 years after the end of the Clinical trial. However, the medical files of subjects shall be archived in accordance with national law.*

XXX

5.3. Duties of the Principal Investigator

The Clinical Site shall ensure that:

- the PI shall oversee the performance of the obligations of the Clinical Site Team Members as set out in this Agreement
- the PI undertakes to use the patient information sheet as provided by Sponsor and approved by the Ethics Committee and to obtain written informed consent from each Study subject or, where the subject is not able to give informed consent, his or her legally designated representative, prior to inclusion or initiation of any Study specific procedures for screening according to the Protocol.

[Specific examples of tasks are provided below (in italics). If not applicable, please delete and/or replace the following examples]

- *sign and date his/her CV and send it to the Sponsor.*
- *shall ensure compliance of a Clinical trial at a Clinical Site with the requirements of this Regulation.*
- *shall assign tasks among the members of the team of investigators and in a way which is not compromising the safety of subjects and the reliability and robustness of the data generated in the Clinical trial at that Clinical trial site.*
- *ensure qualification of all Clinical Trial Member at the Clinical Site regarding their respective tasks according to the Protocol.*
- *ensure completion and verification of all the data in the case report form (CRF).*

- *report and assess deviations from the protocol according to existing procedures.*
- *ensure that an informed consent is obtained for each participant in the Clinical trial.*

The PI must strictly comply with the obligations set forth at the applicable law.

5.4. Duties delegated by the Sponsor to third parties and obligations of the Clinical site in relation to these tasks *[If not applicable, please delete this section]*

[Specific examples of tasks are provided below (in italics). If not applicable, please delete and/or replace the following examples]

- *The Clinical Site acknowledges and agrees that the Sponsor has delegated certain tasks to third parties as Described in the Task list (see Appendix 1).*
- *The Clinical Site agrees to support the Sponsor and its third parties to perform the delegated tasks on behalf of the Sponsor.*
- *The Sponsor guarantee that the same level of Confidentiality as described in the present Agreement shall be imposed upon xxx;*

- *Consequently, the Clinical site shall cooperate and ensure that such third parties access to all information, documents and data necessary for the performance of the delegated tasks.*

5.4.1. Duties delegated to the national Coordinating centre [*Insert name of the delegated institution*] *[If not applicable, delete this section]*

[Describe the Duties delegated to the national Coordinating centre and the role of the Clinical site in relation to these duties; Specific examples of tasks are provided below (in italics). If not applicable, please delete and/or replace the following examples]

The Clinical site acknowledges and agrees that the responsibility for performing the following tasks has been delegated by the Sponsor to the national coordinator centre:

- *to ensure the coordination of the Clinical Sites in the country*
- *to ensure the recruitment follow up*

*Consequently, the Clinical site shall: **[Describe the Role of the Clinical site]***

- *.....*

5.4.2. Duties delegated by the Sponsor to a Clinical Trial Unit (CTU)/Clinical Research Organization (CRO) via a separate agreement and that might have an impact on the relationship between the Sponsor and the Clinical site **[If not applicable, please delete this section]**

[Describe the Duties delegated to a third party and the role of the Clinical site in relation to these duties]

[Specific examples of tasks are provided below (in italics). If not applicable, please delete and/or replace the following examples]

- *The Sponsor has delegated to [Insert name of the delegated institution] the following tasks:
 - *coordinate and perform the regulatory submissions in the countries...*
 - *ensure the central monitoring of the Clinical trial**
- *For xxx to perform its delegated Tasks, the Clinical site should:
for XXX to perform the monitoring related Tasks, the Clinical site shall ensure that XXX has access to the Raw data as per the procedure described in the Monitoring Manual and approved by the ethics committee and any other authorities in the country. **[Describe the procedure in a few words and/or attach the Monitoring Manual]***
- *Should the Task delegation list change, the Agreements does not require amendment; the Clinical Site shall simply be notified in writing by the Sponsor.*
- ***For a detailed description of the Delegated tasks, see Appendix xxx, Task delegation list***

5.4.5. In addition, the Sponsor contracted the transfer of Human Biological material to *[Insert name of the delegated institution]* via a separate agreement and that might have an impact on the relationship between the Sponsor and the Clinical site **[If not applicable, please delete this section]**

For xxx to ensure the transfer of the biological material on behalf of the Sponsor, the Clinical site shall [Describe the obligations of the Clinical site]

- *Xxxx*

6. RULES REGARDING THE PROCESSING AND TRANSFER OF PERSONAL DATA

Please check if this wording of this section is in line with your national provisions; if not, provide in the Annex the rules applicable [Country specific Annex]

For all work involving the processing of personal data, including but not limited to medical information and genetic information, the Parties shall fully comply with prevailing data protection provisions, in particular the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation) and any related law and regulations applicable in the concerned countries.

The Parties shall ensure that any applicable authorization and opinion from relevant supervisory authorities and informed consents from the Data Subjects – if so far needed under applicable law- required for performing the Tasks or to conduct of Clinical trial will be obtained prior to the commencement of the respective tasks.

OPTION 1 [the Clinical trial is funded under an EU funding program, both Parties are Beneficiaries and the data processing rules/agreement have been already established under the EU Consortium agreement or any other specific DPA Agreement; in this case, a reference to the previous rules/agreement should be sufficient]: The Parties must process personal data involved in the activities in compliance with the rules established under the Grant Agreement and/or the Consortium Agreement, as well as the specific the terms and conditions as set out in Appendix **xxx** of this Agreement.

OPTION 2 [the Clinical trial is not funded under an EU funding program or in case it is, the rules regarding the data protection activities in the context of the Clinical trial haven't been defined in detail; or Clinical trial outside the EU funding program]:

Each Party must fulfil its obligations according to its role and responsibilities under the GDPR and as defined in the present Agreement (data controller, data processor, data sub-processor), shall assist the other Party in meeting such obligations and shall provide the other Party with all the information that is needed to show that such obligations have been met.

The Parties acknowledge and agree that the following data processing activities will be performed in the context of the present Agreement:

(1) Personal data processing and transfer activities necessary for the performance of the tasks related to the Clinical Trial as described in the Task list (Purpose 1) (see Appendix xx)

o Any data involved in the performance of the tasks related to the performance of the Clinical Trial (Purpose 1) shall be processed in accordance with the Rules set forth in **Appendix xxx** below, as well as with the relevant data protection laws and regulations.

The Parties acknowledges and agree that any national specifics should be attached to this Agreement as an Appendix.

The Sponsor will transfer pseudonymized Clinical trial data related to EEA/EU data subjects for the purpose of XXX [e.g. Data management] to xxx which is based and registered in the following non EEA/EU country: **xxx**.

According to the GDPR, the processing of personal data outside -EEA/EU country under the Agreement shall be considered a transfer to a third country and thus shall take place in accordance with the conditions laid down in Chapter V GDPR “Transfers of personal data to third countries or international organizations”.

The Clinical Site Institution together with the PI shall ensure that appropriate information concerning such transfers has been provided to the research participants within the information process and, depending on the national laws and regulation, an appropriate legal basis is available for such transfers (e.g. consent of data subjects, public interest, etc)

(2) Personal Data processing activities necessary for the administration of contractual relationships and any related communications. (Purpose 2)

o Any data involved in the administration of the contractual relationship such as agreement preparation, negotiations, and follow up as well as any communications, meetings, etc. performed in the context of the Agreement shall be processed in accordance with the Rules set forth below, as well as with the relevant data protection laws and regulations.

(3) Personal Data processing for further research purposes (secondary use) (Purpose 3)

The Clinical site acknowledges and agrees that, upon the termination of the Clinical trial and subject to compliance with the relevant laws and regulations, the patient consent or another legal basis as applicable, the Clinical trial related data shall be used and shared by the Sponsor with third parties for further research purposes. The Sponsor will keep the Clinical site informed of such use.

Consequently, the Clinical site agrees to support the Sponsor in fulfilling this purpose by :

[Specific examples of tasks are provided below (in italics). If not applicable, please delete and/or replace them with the appropriate tasks]:

- *Tailoring the Clinical trial related documents, including but not limited to the patient's information notice document, for this purpose as per the model developed by the Sponsor.*

- *When this is under the Clinical site responsibility, ensuring that all the legal and regulatory authorisations and permissions have been obtained in accordance with the national laws and regulations*
-

Should additional data processing activities be necessary in the context of the present Agreement, the Agreement shall be modified accordingly.

7. RULES REGARDING THE PROCESSING AND TRANSFER OF HUMAN BIOLOGICAL MATERIAL

[Model responsibilities clauses are provided below (in italics). If not applicable, please delete and/or replace it with the appropriate clauses]:

- *The Clinical site acknowledges and agrees that the Sponsor shall use human biological materials for the purpose of the research, subject to informed consent as applicable and in accordance with applicable laws and requirements.*
- *The Clinical site shall promptly comply with any request from the Sponsor requiring the Clinical site to transfer Biological Material to.... Further, in addition to the requirements of this Agreement, the Clinical*

site shall cooperate fully with the Sponsor in implementing such further measures as Sponsor may reasonably require protecting Biological Material in accordance with legal and regulatory protection requirements, including but not limited to the information and consent of the research participants, ...

- *Each Party shall ensure that any collection, handling, traceability, transportation, retention and storage of biological materials are carried out in accordance with the Protocol (and any specific procedure for biobanking and processing of associated personal data), the agreed quality procedures, the research participants rights, including the informed consent as applicable, and all applicable laws and requirements.*

- *Each party should ensure that the security, integrity and quality of the biological materials are maintained at all times.*
- *In case of transfer of required research samples from Clinical site to **XXX** , the transfer shall be handled by **xxx**.*
- *The samples will be stored in accordance with the requirements laid down by all applicable laws, regulations and guidelines, in particular in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and with the principles of good clinical practice as laid down by the ICH E6 R3, and the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation) and any related law and regulations applicable in the concerned countries.*

- Should the Sponsor express interest in analyzing samples owned by the Clinical Site, the Sponsor will assume all costs related to the shipment and analysis of said samples

8. COST AND PAYMENTS

[Several model clauses are provided below, depending on the source of funding: General rules (regardless of the source of funding), model clauses if Horizon Europe Funding, model clauses if not Horizon Europe funding]

8.1. GENERAL RULES

For the performance of the Tasks, both Parties agree on the costs, which are based on the assumptions described in Appendix *xx [see Appendix xxx]*.

The total budget for the execution of the Tasks by the Clinical site is *[insert total budget amount]* euros and the amount per participant xxxx euros.

The agreed costs are valid for the entire Agreement period and shall not be subject to any adjustment. In the event that amendments to the Protocol and/or to the Tasks assigned to the Clinical site (including but not limited to change in the number of Clinical Trial participants per trial site) require changes to the budget

allocated to the Clinical site and/or to the Sponsor – Clinical site financial arrangements, such changes shall be notified to SPONSOR beforehand and without delay and shall be subject to the Parties prior approval.

Payments will be made pro-rata for work completed. On a quarterly basis *[This is subject to prior agreement between the Parties]*, the Clinical site shall submit original invoice(s) and report summarizing the work completed at the address below.

Electronic invoices or copies of the original hard copies will be sent by Clinical Site to the following email: xxxxx.

The Clinical Trial's reference *[project acronym]* should be mentioned on the invoice. Invoices for the work completed will be paid within thirty (30) days of receipt.

INVOICING DETAILS: *[Insert details: address, email, etc.]*

The last invoice shall be dated and sent to Sponsor no later than the end date of the Agreement, which is *dd/mm/yyyy*.

In the event of early termination of the Agreement, if payment (whether for salaries or otherwise) has been made by Sponsor to Clinical site in advance for work not completed, funds received in advance at the exception of duly justified expenses already incurred by Clinical site, shall be returned to Sponsor within thirty (30) days of the effective date of termination.

Misuse of funds, if discovered or suspected, will result in immediate suspension of the Tasks and reimbursement of the already received funds shall/may be expected.

Select the right Model: 1 (EU Funding) with Options depending on the status of the Parties under the EU Grant agreement; or Model 2: Other source of funding

MODEL 1 : CLINICAL TRIALS FUNDED EXCLUSIVELY UNDER EU FUNDING PROGRAMS ARE PROVIDED BELOW; several OPTIONS ARE PROVIDED BELOW; THE FINANCIAL RULES ARE DEPENDENT ON THE STATUS OF THE PARTIES UNDER THE EU GRANT AGREEMENT: BENEFICIARY, AFFILIATED PARTNER/LINK TO THE BENEFICIARY, SUBCONTRACTOR or IN KIND.]

[Please select the appropriate OPTION if the Clinical trial is funded exclusively under an EU funding program]

OPTION 1: Both Parties are a BENEFICIARY under the EU Grant Agreement

- The Sponsor and the Clinical site are beneficiaries to the EU GA *[Insert GA Acronym]*.
- The reference number of the Beneficiaries under the GA is *[Insert the Beneficiary reference number under the GA]*
- Consequently, the handling of the financial matters will be performed as outlined in the Grant Agreement. For the avoidance of any doubt, the budget allocated to the Parties under the GA and the budget breakdown have been attached to the Agreement in Appendix XXX.

- If amendments to the Protocol and/or to the Tasks (including but not limited to change in the number of Clinical Trial participants per trial site, addition of a Clinical Trial site) require changes to the budget and/or to the financial arrangements between the Parties, the Clinical site shall notify the Sponsor in writing without delay.
- Any amendments to the financial provisions of the Agreement shall be made in writing as an amendment to the Agreement and shall take into consideration the funding principles and the budget set out in the Grant Agreement and the possibility of a financial re-arrangement is not possible within the EU GA.

OPTION 2: Linked or belong to the BENEFICIARY (Affiliated party or a department related to the Beneficiary)

- For the avoidance of any doubt, xxx is linked to the following Beneficiary *[Insert name/legal details of the Beneficiary and its reference number under the GA]*
- The budget for the execution of the Tasks by the Clinical site, for a total amount of *[Insert amount]* euros (direct costs plus **xxx** overheads) has been directly allocated to *[name Beneficiary]* as beneficiary to the Grant Agreement. Consequently, the payment of Clinical site (or of the Sponsor) for the performance of Tasks will be performed by the Beneficiary as outlined in the aforementioned Grant Agreement.

- For the avoidance of any doubt, xxx shall not bear any liability or responsibility which may arise in connection with the payment of xxx as the budget has been allocated directly to the Beneficiary.
- In the event that amendments to the Protocol and/or to the Tasks (including but not limited to change in the number of Clinical Trial participants per trial site, addition of a Clinical Trial site) require changes to the budget and/or financial arrangements, such changes shall be notified to the Sponsor and to the coordinator of the EU GA without delay.
- For the avoidance of any doubt, such changes to the Clinical Trial financing arrangements shall take into consideration the funding principles and the budget set out in Grant Agreement and shall be subject to a prior agreement between the coordinator of the EU GA and the Beneficiary.
 - Following the formal approval by the coordinator of the EU GA, this Agreement shall be amended accordingly.
 - “The budget breakdown agreed in the aforementioned Grant Agreement is attached as Appendix (see Appendix 2)”

OPTION 3: The Clinical site is a subcontractor or a third party providing in-kind contribution to Sponsor under the EU GA.

- The Clinical site is considered a *[Select if subcontractor or in-kind party]* under the EU Grant agreement.

- For the performance of the Tasks, both Parties agree on the costs, which are based on the assumptions described in Appendix *xxx [see Appendix xxx]*.
- The total budget for the execution of the Tasks by the Clinical site is *[insert total budget amount]* euros (all included, VAT excluded).
- The agreed costs are valid for the entire Agreement period and shall not be subject to any adjustment.
- In the event that amendments to the Protocol and/or to the Tasks (including but not limited to change in the number of Clinical Trial participants per trial site, addition of a Clinical Trial site) require changes to the budget and/or financial arrangements, such changes shall be notified to the Sponsor beforehand and without delay and shall be subject to the Parties prior approval.
- Upon such approval, the Agreement shall be amended accordingly and shall take into consideration the funding principles and the budget set out in the EU Grant Agreement.
- Payments will be made pro-rata for work completed. On a quarterly basis, Clinical site shall submit original invoice(s) and report summarizing the work completed at the address below.
- Electronic invoices or copies of the original hard copies will be sent by e-mail. The Clinical Trial's reference *[EU project acronym]* should be mentioned on the invoice. Invoices for the work completed will be paid within thirty (30) days of receipt.

INVOICING DETAILS: *[Insert details: address, email, etc.]*

- The last invoice shall be dated and sent to Sponsor no later than the end date of the Agreement, which is *dd/mm/yyyy*. No invoice will be accepted for payment after the end of the Agreement.
- In the event of early termination of the Agreement, if payment (whether for salaries or otherwise) has been made by Sponsor to Clinical site in advance for work not completed, funds received in advance at the exception of duly justified expenses already incurred by Clinical site, shall be returned to Sponsor within thirty (30) days of the effective date of termination.
- Misuse of funds, if discovered or suspected, will result in immediate suspension of the Tasks and reimbursement of the already received funds shall/may be expected.

CLAUSES RELATED TO REPORTING PERIODS IF APPLICABLE UNDER THE EU GA:

- According to the Grant Agreement action is divided into the ‘reporting periods’ as follows:

[Example to be modified according to the project schedule:]

RP1: from month 01 to month 12 (01/09/2017 – 31/08/2018)

RP2: from month 13 to month 24 (01/09/2018 – 31/08/2019)

RP3: from month 25 to month 36 (01/09/2019 – 31/08/2020)

RP4: from month 37 to month 48 (01/09/2020 – 31/08/2021)

RP5: from month 49 to month 60 (01/09/2021 – 31/08/2022)

- Consequently, the payment of Clinical site for the performance of Tasks will be performed following reporting periods as outlined in the aforementioned Grant Agreement, and described in Appendix 2, **The Parties acknowledges and agree that any national specifics should be attached to this Agreement as an Appendix.**

MODEL 2: Other funding models

The budget and compensation to be paid for the Study is included in Appendix B. Payment shall be due and payable in accordance with the schedule and details set forth in Appendix B. All invoiced amounts are exclusive of VAT, if applicable, and subject to overhead according to applicable law.

The Parties acknowledge and agree that the compensation and support provided by Sponsor to Institution pursuant to this Agreement represents the fair market value for the Study conducted by Institution, has been negotiated in an arms-length transaction, and has not been determined in a manner that takes into account the volume or value of any referrals or other business otherwise generated between Sponsor and Institution. Nothing contained in this Agreement should be construed in any manner as an obligation or inducement for the Institution to recommend that any person or entity purchase the Sponsor's products or those of any entity affiliated with Sponsor.

Institutions shall not bill any third party for any Study Drug(s) or other items or services furnished by Sponsor in connection with the Study, or any services provided to Study subjects in connection with the Study for which payment is made as part of the Study.

Changes to the Protocol: In the event of a change to the Study Protocol that results in an increased cost, or if any increase in compensation is necessary or appropriate for proper conduct of the Study, the Parties shall negotiate further compensation. If the Parties agree to such an increase in compensation, the Sponsor shall provide written notice to the Institution in the form of a budget increase letter

9. LIABILITY AND INDEMNIFICATION

9.1. Liability and indemnification rules

Option 1: in case the Clinical site institution is not self-insured

Option 1.1. : Model applicable in most of the countries

Each Party agrees to defend, indemnify and hold harmless) the other Party, its agents and employees (collectively the "Other Party's Indemnitees") from all claims, actions, suits, proceedings, liability, losses, damages, charges, orders, fines and expenses, including attorneys' fees and expenses, arising out of activities pursuant to the Clinical Trial, including but not limited to:

- a. errors or omissions, negligence or wilful misconduct, by the Party, its directors, agents, employees or third parties pertaining to the activities to be carried out pursuant to the obligations under this Agreement.

- b. violations of applicable law and regulations related to the conduct of the Clinical Trial by Party, its directors, agents, employees or third parties acting on behalf of the Party; or
- c. breaches of any provision of this Agreement.

Each Party shall promptly notify the other in writing of any such complaint, claim or injury relating to any loss subject to this indemnification.

Option 1.2. : Alternative model provided by Czech Republic (to be arbitrated)

The Sponsor declares that, in accordance with Section 58(2) of Act No. 378/2007 Coll., on Pharmaceuticals, as amended, it has arranged liability insurance for the Investigator and the Clinical Site for the entire duration of the clinical trial. This insurance also covers compensation in the event of the death of a study subject or harm to the health of a study subject caused by participation in the clinical trial. A copy of the insurance certificate is attached as an annexe to this Agreement.

The Sponsor undertakes to indemnify the Clinical Site and the Principal Investigator for any harm to the health of a study subject, in the amount of a claim successfully asserted in court by the subject or their legal representative. Such a claim must relate exclusively to harm to the health of a subject who duly participated in the clinical trial and must have arisen as a direct consequence of the clinical trial, the use of the investigational medicinal product, or procedures used in accordance with the clinical trial protocol.

The Sponsor shall not be obliged to provide compensation for harm to health to the extent that it proves that:

- a) the harm to the subject's health was caused wholly or partly by the fault of the study subject or their legal representative; or
 - b) the harm to the subject's health was wholly or partly caused by unlawful, intentional, or negligent conduct, or other breaches of obligations imposed on the Clinical Site, the Principal Investigator, or their collaborators by law or this Agreement; or
 - c) the Clinical Site failed to notify the Sponsor that such a claim for compensation had been made within 30 (thirty) days from the date the claim was raised, or at the latest within 30 (thirty) days from the date it became or should have become aware of such claim; or
 - d) the Clinical Site acknowledged a compensation claim made by a study subject without obtaining the Sponsor's prior written consent;
 - e) medical and other documentation relating to the harm caused by participation in the clinical trial was not maintained in such a way as to enable detailed reconstruction of and evaluation of the Clinical trial.
- The Clinical Site or the Principal Investigator shall inform the Sponsor of all circumstances that may reasonably be assumed to give rise to a claim or legal proceedings, of which they are directly aware, and shall keep the Sponsor reasonably informed of the development of such a claim or proceedings, even if the Clinical Site and Principal Investigator decide not to assert a claim for compensation under these conditions. Similarly, the Sponsor shall inform the Clinical Site and the Principal Investigator of all such circumstances and the development of.

The Clinical Site declares that it has in place valid liability insurance covering damage arising in connection with the provision of healthcare services, in accordance with legal regulations

The Sponsor's obligations set out in this Article of the Agreement shall remain valid even after the termination of this Agreement.

The Sponsor shall not be entitled, without the prior written consent of the Clinical Site, to acknowledge any fault on the part of the Clinical Site or the Investigator when handling claims from third parties.

Option 2: In the event the Clinical site institution is self-insured (model provided by Denmark; similar rules may apply in other countries in similar situations)

Sponsor shall defend, indemnify and hold harmless Institution, its trustees, officers, agents and employees (including the Principal Investigator and any Study personnel) from any and all losses, costs, expenses, liabilities, claims, actions and damages (collectively "Claims"), based on a personal injury or death to a Study subject caused by i) the use of the Study Drug during the course of the Study and ii) any other Protocol procedures performed pursuant to this Agreement.

The Sponsor's obligation to indemnify the Institution shall not apply to the extent that any Claim results from the Institution's (including the Principal Investigator's and/or any Study personnel's): a) failure to adhere to the terms of the Protocol or IB or (b) failure to comply with any applicable standards or other governmental laws, rules, regulations or requirements or (c) any acts of gross negligence or willfull misconduct.

Institution as a public Danish body is self-insured according to Danish law. Institution's assets are sufficient to cover any contemplated self-insured liability assumed by Institution under this Agreement. All Study

subjects are covered by Danish mandatory law "Lov om klage- og erstatningsadgang inden for sundhedsvæsenet, kapitel 4 (lov nr. 547 af 24. juni 2005)" as amended from time to time. Institution shall not be liable for any indirect losses, consequential damages, operational losses, loss of profit or other consequential financial losses.

Sponsor agrees to abide by the guidelines in relation to compensation for injuries suffered by Study subject included in the Study in accordance with applicable legislation and provisions of Denmark (Bekendtgørelse af lov om produktansvar (lov nr. 61 af 20 marts 2007) and Lov om klage- og erstatningsadgang indenfor sundhedsvæsenet (lov nr. 547 af 24. juni 2005) as amended from time to time.

Sponsor carries general liability and product liability. Sponsor shall secure and maintain in full force and effect through-out the performance of the Study (and following termination of the Study to cover any claims arising from the Study) insurance coverage for i) product and study design liability and ii) general liability, each such insurance coverage in amounts appropriate to cover the Sponsor's obligations and liabilities under this Agreement and in compliance with the applicable legal and regulatory requirements.

Upon request, Sponsor shall provide Institution with certificates of insurance evidencing the required insurance coverage.

9.2. Limitations of contractual liability

No Party shall be responsible to any other Party for any indirect or consequential loss or similar damage such as, but not limited to, loss of profit, loss of revenue or loss of contracts, except in case of breach of confidentiality.

Additional provisions could be added if the Clinical trial is conducted within the scope of a EU FUNDING Project and both parties are Beneficiaries to the GA and the CA] [Here below an extract of the Liability and indemnification provisions extracted from a standard Consortium Agreement] [Please make sure that the Liability section under this Agreement is aligned with the liabilities provisions agreed upon as Beneficiaries under the Consortium Agreement to the extend applicable to the Trial]:

- **No warranties**
- *In respect of any information or materials (incl. Results and Background) supplied by one Party to another under the Project, no warranty or representation of any kind is made, given or implied as to sufficiency or fitness for purpose nor as to the absence of any infringement of any proprietary rights of Third Parties.*
- *Therefore, the recipient Party shall in all cases be entirely and solely liable for the use to which it puts such information and materials unless the disclosing Party failed to provide relevant information, including instruction or recommendations, only known to it, and the information would have prevented the relevant damages, and*

- *No Party granting Access Rights shall be liable for any infringement of proprietary rights of a Third Party resulting from any other Party (or its entities under the same control) exercising its Access Rights unless the provision of such Results or Background, or the granting of Access Rights on such Results or Background, was made by the providing Party in breach of Third Parties' rights. Insofar as the Parties hereto are aware of Third-Party rights, they shall notify the other Party without delay.*
- ***Limitations of contractual liability***
- *No Party shall be responsible to any other Party for any indirect or consequential loss or similar damage such as, but not limited to, loss of profit, loss of revenue or loss of contracts, except in case of breach of confidentiality.*
- *A Party's general aggregate liability towards the other Parties collectively shall be limited to once the Beneficiary's share of the total costs of the Project as identified in Annex 2 of the Grant Agreement provided and in case of Associated Partners to the total amount of its estimated costs. The limitation to the Beneficiaries' general aggregate liability also applies to Affiliated Entities.*
- *A Party's liability shall not be limited under either of the two foregoing paragraphs to the extent such damage was caused by a wilful act or gross negligence or to the extent that such limitation is not permitted by law.*
- *The terms of this Consortium Agreement shall not be construed to amend or limit any Party's statutory liability.*

10. INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RULES (IPR)

[Please select the Option that best corresponds to your situation]

OPTION 1: [When both Parties are Beneficiaries to an EU Funded project. Usually, the IP Rules are established and discussed as part of the Consortium agreement; Ideally, an agreement should be reached on the IP and Background in advance, at the proposal preparation stage; not to block the signature of the CSA, a simple reference to the relevant IP provisions included in the CA should suffice)

The ownership and the dissemination of results of the Clinical Trial shall comply with the terms set forth in the Consortium Agreement *[Final Version, Insert version number and date]* and the specific Grant Agreement *[Insert reference number]*.

Or

OPTION 2: [if IP rules are not defined in the CA (EU funded project) or if the Clinical trial is not conducted within the framework of an EU funding program framework; several approaches are possible; we have selected here the most commonly used]

OPTION 2.1.: The Sponsor is the owner of the Results; the Clinical site/Investigator are considered service providers

The Clinical Site and the Investigator acknowledge and agree that the data and results obtained during or in relation to the conduct of the Trial under this Agreement (hereinafter referred as to "Data and Results") belong to the Sponsor.

Clinical Site and the Investigator agree not to make claims to possible intellectual property rights (the "IPR") from Data and Result obtained during or in relation to the conduct of the Clinical Trial and not to pursue IPR protection that would prevent or block access to or use of any data, conclusions drawn directly from those Data and Results.

Background IP shall be made freely available to all the Parties solely for the purpose and for the duration of the Clinical Trial.

Clinical Site shall, however, retain ownership of any patient or medical records, personal notes and other source documentation.

Clinical Site/Principal Investigator retain right to use Data and Results for further internal research, education and patientcare purposes.

In the event that the Sponsor intends to register ownership of rights for aspects resulting from the Clinical trial, the Clinical Site and the Principal Investigator shall comply with any necessary procedures for this purpose, which are the sole responsibility of the Sponsor, at Sponsor's full cost.

However, all data, intellectual property rights and know how ("Background IP") owned by a Party prior to the date of this Agreement other than any data, intellectual property rights and know how arising from the Clinical trial are and shall remain the property of that Party.

Option 2.2: Each Party is considered the owner of its own Results

The data and results obtained during or in relation to the conduct of the Clinical trial (hereinafter referred as to "Data" and "Results") are owned by the Party that generates them. Data and Results created jointly by the Parties shall be jointly owned by the Parties pro rata to their intellectual contribution. If the respective contributions of the Parties cannot be documented, such Data and Results shall be owned by the Parties in equal shares. All disposal of jointly owned Data and Results shall require agreement between the Parties.

Background IP shall be made freely available to all the Parties solely for the purpose and for the duration of the Clinical trial.

However, all data, intellectual property rights and know how ("Background IP") owned by a Party prior to the date of this Agreement other than any data, intellectual property rights and know how arising from the Clinical trial are and shall remain the property of that Party.

Clinical Site shall, however, retain ownership of any patient or medical records, personal notes and other source documentation.

Clinical Site/Principal Investigator retain right to use Data for further research, education and patientcare purposes.

In the event that the Data and Results were protectable as industrial property rights, the Sponsor and the Clinical Site, which by mutual agreement is considered most appropriate in each case, would be the entity authorised to request the registrations they deem appropriate and to exploit them in the widest manner permitted by law.

11. CONFIDENTIALITY RULES

All information furnished by the Disclosing Party (“Confidential Information”) pursuant to this Agreement, to the Receiving Party shall be considered confidential and none of the Parties shall, without the prior written permission of the Disclosing Party, disclose the same to any third party other than as required to perform the Clinical trial, except if required by applicable law.

These provisions shall not apply to:

- Any of the information which at the time of receipt by the Receiving Party is in the public domain;
- any of the information which after its receipt by the Receiving Party is made public by a third party acting without impropriety in so doing;

- any of the information which the Receiving Party can establish was in its possession before receipt from the Disclosing Party or was developed independently or acquired directly or indirectly from a source wholly independent of the Disclosing Party;
- any reference to the Clinical Trial made by the participating Centre, by Investigator in the report of its/his activities, that is requested by competent Authorities.

During the Clinical Trial and for a period of five (5) years after its completion or any other period agreed in the supplementary agreement, the Parties and Affiliate of a Party undertake to preserve the confidentiality or any data, documents or other material in relation to the execution of the Clinical Trial.

Nothing shall prevent the disclosure of those parts of Confidential Information which are required to be disclosed by law or by a court order. In such case, the disclosing Party shall provide the other Party with immediate written notice.

A Party may, as far as necessary for the performance of its obligations under this Agreement, disclose Confidential Information to an individual investigator, or to any relevant committee, collaborator, representative and/or agent that needs such Confidential Information to undertake and/or participate in the Clinical trial only if such third parties are bound by similar confidentiality obligations.

In addition, Confidential Information may be disclosed to the extent required by law and for the purposes of patient care.

The Parties agree that the use and disclosure of patient health and medical information is subject to compliance with applicable EU and national data privacy laws. The Parties, therefore, agree to take all reasonable steps to protect the confidentiality of any patient health and medical information that they have access to and to comply with applicable laws.

12. PUBLICATION AND DISSEMINATION OF RESULTS RULES

[Please select the Option that corresponds best to your situation]

OPTION 1: Parties decide to simply refer to the Vancouver Convention

SPONSOR shall have the right of first publication in a peer-reviewed journal according to the Vancouver convention.

OPTION 2: the Parties define a Protocol for publications

“Protocol for publications” *[To be attached as an Appendix]* must be submitted to the Clinical trial Steering Committee and the proposed publication(s) must be reviewed and accepted by SPONSOR.

OPTION 3: the Parties define specific rules [a model commonly used in this type of agreement is provided below]

Clinical site agrees not to individually publish or present the results it obtains from its participation in the Clinical trial without the prior consent of SPONSOR; such consent shall not unreasonably be withheld.

Upon completion of the Trial, Clinical Site and the Principal Investigator may publish the results, expressly inform the Sponsor and complying with the conditions established in the applicable law. In order to make such a publication, the Sponsor must first be provided with the texts they wish to publish. The Sponsor shall have a period of sixty (60) days to review articles and reports and fifteen (15) days to review posters, abstracts, and other shorter texts.

The Clinical site shall not use the Data for any purpose other than for non-commercial and educational purposes before publication. At the request of the Sponsor, made during the corresponding review period and based on its justified objection due to the need to protect confidential rights, publication must be postponed for a maximum of thirty (30) days.

Notwithstanding the above, in case the Sponsor was involved in a procedure for obtaining a patent on the results of the Clinical trial basis, the Sponsor would be able to postpone its authorization for the publication of the results of the Clinical trial by the Clinical Site and the Principal Investigator until the date of the international registry of such patent.

None of the collaborating partners conducting the Clinical trial including SPONSOR are allowed to withhold from publication data showing negative results.

Notwithstanding the foregoing, if a multi-centre publication is not published within twelve (12) months after completion of the Clinical trial and lock of the Clinical trial database at all research sites that are part of the multi-centre Clinical Study or any earlier termination or abandonment of the Clinical Study, the Clinical site shall have the right to publish or present the methods and results of the Clinical Study in accordance with the provisions of the “Protocol publication”.

The Clinical Site and the Principal Investigator will retain all intellectual property rights established under legislation for their respective publications.

Dissemination of Results rules under the EU Grant Agreement [This rule applies in EU Funded projects. If not applicable, please delete and/or replace] As specified in the aforementioned Grant Agreement, unless the Commission requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) must include the following text: “This project has received funding from the European Union’s xxx research and innovation program under grant agreement *[Insert registration number]*.”

Option 4: Model provided for Denmark (either to be arbitrated between countries or to be inserted into the Country specific Annex as provisions specific to Denmark)

The Parties recognize that Danish law places an obligation on hospitals carrying out health and social care research to publish their work. The Parties agree that this Section 12 should be interpreted in consideration of such obligation.

Following completion of the Study, Sponsor shall use all reasonable endeavors to ensure the appropriate publication or other dissemination of the conclusions of the Study, and Institution/Principal Investigator for such Study shall not publish Data (defined in Section 6) derived from the Study until the results from the Study has been published in a publication by Sponsor. If such publication is not submitted within twelve (12) months after conclusion, abandonment or termination of the Study, or after the Sponsor confirms there will be no publication, Institution/Principal Investigator may publish, present or release the Data from the Study individually in accordance with this Section 12.

If the Study is part of a multi-centre study, then following completion of the entire Study at all sites, Sponsor shall use all reasonable endeavors to ensure the appropriate publication or other dissemination of the conclusions of the Study, and Institution/Principal Investigator for such Study shall not publish Data derived from the Study until the combined results from the entire Study has been published in a joint, multi-centre publication. If such a multi-centre publication is not submitted within twelve (12) months after conclusion, abandonment or termination of the Study at all sites, or after the Sponsor confirms there will be no multi-

centre publication, Institution/Principal Investigator may publish, present or release the Data from the Institution individually in accordance with this Section 12.

If Institution/Principal Investigator wish to publish, present or release Data from the Study, a copy of the manuscript must be provided to the Sponsor for review at least thirty (30) days prior to submission for publication, presentation or release. The Sponsor and Principal Investigator will arrange expedited reviews for abstracts, poster presentations or other materials. Within this thirty (30) day period, the Sponsor shall review such proposed publication, presentation or release to determine whether it contains any Confidential Information of Sponsor (as defined in Section 3), or whether Sponsor desires to file patent applications on subject matter contained therein. Upon receiving any notification from Sponsor requesting deletion of Confidential Information or requesting a delay in publication to allow the filing of patent applications, Principal Investigator shall take the requested action; provided however, that any delay in publication shall not exceed ninety (90) days from the date on which Sponsor received the draft manuscript for review.

13. INSPECTION AND AUDIT RULES

- The Clinical site shall allow any national regulatory authorities to inspect the Clinical trial on site and shall promptly notify SPONSOR of such inspection and SPONSOR shall have the right to be present at any such inspection or regulatory action.
- The Clinical site will provide a copy to SPONSOR of any subsequent report, recommendations and measures and steps taken.

- The Clinical site shall in accordance with applicable law also allow any audit by the SPONSOR, communicated beforehand and during normal Clinical site working hours, to facilities and data directly related with the clinical trial.
- In case the Clinical site is inspected by a regulatory authority under the performance of the Clinical trial, the Sponsor shall cover the inspection costs, if any.

14. TERM AND TERMINATION OF THE AGREEMENT

14.1. Term of the Agreement

OPTION 1 : This Agreement shall enter into force as from the date of signature of the last Party to sign (effective date) and shall remain in effect until completion of the Clinical trial in accordance with applicable law and regulations, close-out of Institution, completion of the obligations of the Parties under this Agreement or earlier termination in accordance with this Section 14 whichever occurs first.

OPTION 2 (In the context of EU funded projects) : This Agreement shall enter into force as from the date of signature of the last Party to sign (effective date) and shall remain in effect until the end date of the EU Grant, that is xx/xx/xxxx]

Option 3: The execution of the Clinical trial at the Clinical Site will last for an expected duration of __ (__) months (when Option 1 is not acceptable)

The agreement may be extended in writing by amendment. All extension shall be subject to the drafting of an amendment to be signed by an authorized representative of each Party.

14.2. Termination of the Agreement

This Agreement can, only after discussing between the Parties, be terminated by written notice in case of

- a. early termination of the Clinical study and/or of the EU project as applicable
- b. any technical, administrative cause (e.g. Clinical study not authorized, suspended or prohibited by the Authorities) or methodological impossibility to pursue the Clinical trial
- c. termination for Breach
- d. the Principal Investigator becomes unavailable due to death, disability or other reasons beyond the control of Clinical Site and not attributable to Clinical Site's own acts or omissions. However, Clinical Site agrees to first use its best efforts to identify a replacement Principal Investigator acceptable to Sponsor. For the avoidance of doubt, if no acceptable replacement can be found, this will not be deemed a breach of contract.

In the event of a breach by any Party of any of its obligations under this Agreement, the other Party may provide written notice to the breaching Party, such notice specifying the breach and requiring that the default be remedied within sixty (60) days.

If the breach has not been remedied by the breaching Party to the satisfaction of the other Parties within sixty (60) days of receipt by the breaching Party of the notice identifying the breach and requiring its remedy, the Parties may terminate automatically, totally or partially, this Agreement with respect to the Defaulting Party with immediate effect.

Such termination shall become effective with respect to such Defaulting Party as of the date of the notice of termination. Fees in relation with Tasks carried out up to this termination remain payable.

The defaulting Party concerned by the termination undertakes to communicate to the other Party or subrogated third parties, free of charge and immediately, all the files and information required to allow them to continue the performance of the Study.

Exercising this cancellation right does not exonerate the defaulting Party from fulfilling its contracted obligations until the effective date of the termination and shall not, in any case be interpreted as a

waiving, by the Party or Parties requesting the termination, of damages and interest in any way whatsoever.

15. SURVIVAL

The rights and obligations of the Parties which by intent or meaning have validity beyond termination as set forth above, including, but not limited to, rights with respect to patent rights, ownership of Data and Results, confidentiality, liability, indemnification and insurance, and publication shall survive termination or expiration of this Agreement, unless otherwise expressly agreed under the Agreement.

16. FORCE MAJEURE

No Party shall be considered to be in breach of this Agreement if such breach is caused by force majeure. Each Party shall notify the other Party of any force majeure as soon as possible. If impossibility or delay in fulfilment due to a case of force majeure continues for longer than three (3) months, the latter Party may automatically terminate the Agreement at any time by written notification sent to the other Party.

17. NOTICES

All notices or other communications required or permitted to be made or given hereunder shall be deemed so made or given when hand-delivered, by e-mail, or sent in writing by registered or certified

mail, postage prepaid and return-receipt requested, or by a recognized courier service, charges prepaid and properly addressed to the representatives of the Parties at their addresses mentioned herein:

SPONSOR

[Insert contact details]

CLINICAL SITE

[Insert contact details]

18. DISPUTES, LAW GOVERNING THE CONTRACT AND JURISDICTION

If any dispute arises out of this Agreement the Parties shall first attempt to resolve the matter informally through designated senior representatives of each Party to the dispute, who are not otherwise involved with the Clinical trial.

If the Parties are not able to resolve the dispute informally within a reasonable time not exceeding two (2) months from the date the informal process is requested by notice in writing, the Parties hereby consent to and agree that the competent courts of **the country where Clinical Site is located**, shall have the sole and exclusive jurisdiction.

This Agreement and all disputes arising hereunder will be governed by and interpreted in accordance with the **laws of the country where the Clinical Site is located**.

19. MISCELLANEOUS

This Agreement, including the attached Appendixes constitutes the entire and only Agreement between the parties relating to the Clinical trial, and all prior negotiations, representations, agreements, and understandings are superseded hereby.

This Agreement may only be modified through a written amendment signed by authorised representatives of all Parties and specifically referring to this Agreement.

The invalidity of one or more provisions of this agreement does not affect the validity of the others. The invalid provision is to be replaced by a provision, which, in compliance with the legal prescriptions, suits the purpose best.

The modification shall be made in writing and approved by mutual agreement of authorized representatives of all the Parties as specified in article Terms and Termination.

Should there be any inconsistency between the Protocol and the terms of this Agreement, or any other document incorporated therein the Agreement shall prevail, except with respect to medical or clinical matters for which the provisions of the Protocol shall take precedence.

Neither Party should use the name, logo or emblem of the other Party in any manner for advertising or other promotional purposes without written consent of an authorized staff member of the Party concerned.

The Clinical Site confirms that neither it, and to the best of its knowledge nor any of its investigators, employees, agents or other personnel providing services for the Study pursuant to this Agreement, has ever been prohibited, disqualified, or banned from conducting research by the competent authority or any equivalent regulatory authority..

None of the Parties has a power to assign or transfer its rights and obligations under this Agreement, whether wholly or in part, to any third party without prior written notice to the other Parties

In case of any contradiction between the provisions of this Contract and the provisions of the Grant Agreement and/or the Consortium Agreement, these shall prevail over the Agreement provisions. Therefore, the conflicting provision(s) shall be held invalid, and the subject matter of such provision(s) shall be governed by the relevant provision(s) of the Grant Agreement and/or the Consortium Agreement. In addition, in case of any Clinical trial aspect is not regulated in this Agreement, it is governed by the Grant Agreement and/or the Consortium Agreement.

20. APPENDICES

The following documents are appended to the Agreement and form an integral part hereof:

- Appendix 1: Tasks List Version n° **0X, xx/xx/xxxx**
- Appendix 2: Protocol Version n° **0X, xx/xx/xxxx**
- Appendix 3 : Budget Agreement, Version n° **0X, xx/xx/xxxx**
- Appendix 4: Data protection clause in case the clinical site is Spanish

21. SIGNATURE

IN WITNESS WHEREOF, the Parties, acting through their duly authorized representatives, have executed of this Agreement.

1. For and on behalf of **the SPONSOR**

LEGAL REPRESENTATIVE:

DATE: SIGNATURE:

[Insert details]

2. For and on behalf of **CLINICAL SITE:**

LEGAL REPRESENTATIVE:

DATE: SIGNATURE:

[Insert details]

IF APPLICABLE

Acknowledgment by the Co-Sponsor: *[Insert name, function(s)]*

DATE:

SIGNATURE:

Acknowledgment by the Coordinating Investigator: *[Insert name, function(s)]*

DATE:

SIGNATURE:

Acknowledgment by the Principal Investigator: *[Insert name, function(s) and country]*

DATE:

SIGNATURE:

APPENDICES

Appendix 1: TASK ALLOCATION MATRIX

[Several models are being provided below]

Model 1: [Model developed by the University of Oslo University Hospital; some provisions/responsibilities might be specific to Sponsor's based in Norway]

Activity		Sponsor	NCI	PI	Comments
TRIAL DOCUMENTS					
1.	Protocol and amendments	R	C		Delegated to xxx
2.	Informed consent document (ICD) in national language	R	C		Delegated to xxx
3.	SITE specific risk evaluation	C		R	
4.	Translation of documents to national language	R	C		Delegated to xxxx
APPLICATIONS, APPROVALS AND REGISTRATIONS					
5.	Grant application	R			
6.	Application to national competent authority	R	C		Delegated to xxx
7.	Application to Ethics Committee	R			Delegated to xxx

Activity		Sponsor	NCI	PI	Comments
8.	Get insurance in place	R			
9.	Provide labelling text	R	C		Delegated to xxxx
10.	Implementation of approved protocols and informed consent documents	C	R	R	
11.	Set-up Investigator Site File and keep it updated	C	C	R	
12.	Secure all relevant local/hospital approvals	R		C	
CONTRACTS / AGREEMENTS					
13.	Local pharmacies			R	Could also be the Sponsor. This is to be determined
INVESTIGATIONAL MEDICINAL PRODUCT (IMP)					
14.	Ensure the local pharmacy can handle IMP	C		R	
15.	Training of pharmacy staff in IMP handling	R		C	
TRAINING					
16.	ICH GCP training of site staff			R	
17.	Training of site staff in trial specific procedures	R	C	C	
18.	Providing start-up meeting	R	C	C	
19.	Keeping site delegation log updated			R	
MONITORING					

Activity		Sponsor	NCI	PI	Comments
20.	Ensure monitoring agreement in specify country	R	C	C	
Other					

Model 2: to be added following external review

Appendix 2: Budget Breakdown Agreement, Version n° *0X, xx/xx/xxxx* [Model to be developed and tailored to the national requirements; to avoid lengthy negotiations between the Sponsor and the national clinical site institutions, ideally, such national model should be shared beforehand (through the funding applications) and imposed as a model by the funding authorities]

Appendix 3: Protocol of the Clinical trial (*version 0x, xx/xxx/2025*)

Appendix 4 – COUNTRY SPECIFIC PROVISIONS

[This Annex is for country specific provisions that cannot be subject to negotiation due to national legal and regulatory constraints]

4.1. Spain: Clauses from the Spanish Code of Conduct regulating the processing of personal data in the field of clinical trials and other clinical research and pharmacovigilance.

The Parties agree that the Sponsor shall not take part in collecting the data of the participants in the Study.

Consequently, the [Clinical Site/Principal Investigator] shall be responsible for complying with the information and disclosure duty in relation to the participants in the Study, providing them at the time it gives them the informed consent form a specific document containing all information on the processing of their personal data in relation to the Study activities.

The Parties agree that the [Clinical Site/Principal Investigator/ Sponsor] shall be responsible for carrying out the coding of the personal data of the Study participants.

[Option A, where the obligation rests with the Clinical Site/ Principal Investigator]

For these purposes, the Clinical Site/Principal Investigator must use a procedure that ensures the information received by the Sponsor and, in particular, the information contained in the case report forms, contains no identifying information of the participants in the Study. The [Clinical Site/Principal Investigator] undertakes

not to provide the Sponsor with information that allows it to access and know, directly or indirectly, identifying information of the participants in the Study, in particular, but without implying limitation, the [Clinical Site/Principal Investigator] shall in no event provide information on the process it used to code the data.

In addition, the Clinical Site/Principal Investigator shall adopt measures that allow traceability of all access to the personal data in the event of accidental access.

[Option B, where the obligation rests with the Sponsor]

For these purposes, the Parties agree that the Sponsor shall subcontract a third party to perform the coding of the data of the Study participants using a procedure that guarantees the Sponsor will in no event access identifying information of the participants in the Study. The [Clinical Site/Principal Investigator] must provide that third party with the information it may need to carry out the coding. The Sponsor must enter into a data processing contract with that third party in accordance with the requirements of Article 28 of the GDPR, with the particularity that the contract will lay down the Sponsor's express covenant not to give the processor any instruction that could allow the Sponsor to access or know the identifying information and the consequent obligation of the third party to not provide that identifying information unless required for compliance with its legal obligations. [END of Option B]

The [Clinical Site/Principal Investigator] warrants that it will provide no information to the Sponsor that allows it to identify the participants in the Study. In particular, the [Clinical Site/Principal Investigator] undertakes to send the Sponsor the case report forms without the identifying information of the participants

in the Study, and with no information that could allow the Sponsor to know that data, and only associating the data with the code assigned to each participant as provided in this Clause.

The Sponsor, in turn, undertakes not to access documents relating to the Study that contain identifying information of the participants unless required for compliance with its legal obligation or with the good clinical practice guidelines.

The [Clinical Site/Principal Investigator] will act as contact point for the participants in the Study and therefore undertakes to handle all queries that may be made by the participants in relation to the processing of their personal data, and to process their requests to exercise their right of access, rectification, erasure and restriction of processing with the timing stipulated for that purpose in the personal data protection laws and regulations that apply from time to time.

The Sponsor shall be responsible for contracting the monitor and the auditor and shall enter into a data processing contract with each of them in accordance with the terms of Article 28 of the GDPR.

In the event a member of the investigator team that takes part in the Study is not an employee of the Clinical Site, the Clinical Site will be responsible for contracting said member and will execute a confidentiality and secrecy undertaking, as well as a data processing contract, on the terms described in the preceding section.